

INSTRUCTIONS FOR COLLECTING FIELD DATA

In order to ensure adequate homogeneity and consistency of the field data of the project and to be able to integrate them into other European projects (LUCAS-Land Use and Coverage Area frame Survey), as well as the incorporation of metadata, it is necessary to complete the forms for each plot and sampling point.

The presented data corresponds to the result of the survey conducted on all researchers who will be collecting data in the field. These elements are common to all research areas.

The data from the form related to the working plot **will only be taken once**. To facilitate the understanding of the items, the following explanatory document is attached for each section.

DESCRIPTION OF THE ITEMS RELATING TO THE STUDY PLOT

1. Unique identifier of the parcel in the project
2. Estimated age of the olive grove
3. Plantation frame
4. Olive variety
5. Number of trunks of the olive tree
6. Average production data
7. Irrigation
8. Photograph of the plot

1. PLOT IDENTIFIER :

Corresponds to the identifier assigned by the project manager for each plot

SPAIN	GREECE	ITALY	MARROC	PORTUGAL
ES-HD2	GR-HD43	IT-ORG17	MR-HD25	PT-TD41
ES-HD3	GR-ORG32	IT-ORG18	MR-HD28	PT-TD42
ES-HD8	GR-ORG33	IT-ORG19	MR-ORG23	
ES-HD10	GR-ORG34	IT-ORG48	MR-TD24	
ES-HD22	GR-ORG38	IT-ORG49	MR-TD26	
ES-HD40	GR-ORG39	IT-TD16	MR-TD27	
ES-ORG4	GR-ORG45	IT-TD20	MR-TD29	
ES-ORG6	GR-ORG47	IT-TD21		
EN-ORG11	GR-TD30			
EN-ORG12	GR-TD31			
EN-ORG13	GR-TD35			
EN-ORG14	GR-TD36			
ES-TD1	GR-TD37			
ES-TD5	GR-TD44			
ES-TD7	GR-TD46			
ES-TD9				
ES-TD15				

2. ESTIMATED AGE OF THE OLIVE GROVE

- O.1. Very young olive grove (0-10 years)
- O.2. Young olive grove (10-20)
- O.3. Mature olive grove (20-50)
- O.4. Old olive grove (50-100)
- O.5. Very old olive grove (more than 100)

3. PLANTATION FRAME

Relative to the planting distance between olive trees following a pattern. Options

- A: In hedge:**
 Row distance: (a)
 Distance between trunks (b)

B: Rectangular frame. Measure the distance between two trees.

C: Irregular planting. Does not follow any pattern.

4. OLIVE TREE VARIETY

ADRAMITINI	1	LADOLIA	11
ARBEQUINA	2	NOCELLARA DEL BELICE	12
ARDUO	3	PICHOLINE LANGUEDOC	13

CERASUOLA	4	PICHOLINE MAROCAINE	14
COBRANÇOSA	5	PICUAL	15
GIARRAFFA	6	PICUDO	16
HAOUZIA MENARA	7	SIKITITA	17
HOJIBLANCA	8	THROUBOLIA	18
KOLOVI	9	other	19
KORONÉIKI	10		

5. NUMBER OF FEET OF THE OLIVE TREE

6. AVERAGE PRODUCTION DATA

If the data is known, indicate it (Kg/ha)

7. IRRIGATION:

If the plot has an irrigation system, indicate it (Yes/No)

8. PHOTOGRAPH OF THE PLOT (ACCORDING TO DIRECTIVE LUCAS)

<https://eurogeographics.org/wp-content/uploads/2018/04/2.Workshop.pdf>

DESCRIPTION OF THE ITEMS RELATING TO THE SAMPLING POINTS

ITEM

1. WP CODE	5
2. DATE	5
3. HOUR.....	5
4. GPS COORDINATES OF THE SAMPLE POINT.....	6
5. VEGETABLE COVER.....	6
6. PHENOLOGICAL STATUS OF THE OLIVE GROVE	7
7. WEATHER DATA OF THE DAY OF FIELD DATA CAPTURE	7
8. SAMPLING TYPE.....	9
9. DISTANCE TO THE TREE FROM THE SAMPLE POINT in cm.....	10
10. SAMPLE DEPTH (CM, MM)	10
11. DATA OF THE PEOPLE WHO TAKE THE FIELD DATA	10
12. OBSERVATIONS:	10

1. WP CODE

It corresponds to the Soil O-Live project work package code. i.e. WP.5.1 , WP.5.3, WP.4.1,

2. DATE

Incorporate the date following the ISO 8601 standard: **year-month-day (YYYY-MM-DD)**

Representation according to ISO 8601	possible values
Year and)	YYYY, four digits
month (M)	MM, from 01 to 12
Day D)	DD, day from 1 to 31

i.e. .: 2023-09-14

3. HOUR

Enter the time following the ISO 8601 standard) hh:mm:ss

Hour (H)	hh , from 00 to 23, 24:00:00 as last minute
----------	---

i.e. .: 20:15:00

4. GPS COORDINATES OF THE SAMPLE POINT.

General indications :

1. Identify the WayPoints : Put an identifier to each sample point in the GPS
2. Do not take points under trees with a large crown diameter, since the GPS signal decreases. If necessary, take several points around the tree.
3. Wait a few seconds until the accuracy improves (greater number of satellites available)
4. To obtain a more accurate altitude (Z) place the GPS on the ground when taking the point
5. Data download: as far as possible, download the GPS track points to the computer (if you don't know how to do it, contact the WP 7.1 team, tell us the GPS model and we will tell you how to do it)¹
6. Put the following configuration in the GPS :

To unify the coordinates of all the sampling points, the WGS84 World Geodetic System (World geodetic System 1984) decimal degrees (DD) (with six decimal digits)

Do NOT use UTM projected coordinates, as it can cause confusion when using different ZONES depending on the country in which you work.

SETTINGS

satellite system	GPS+GLONASS WAAS/ egnos : on
Time	Choose 24 hour time setting. Time Zone: automatic
units	Metric Elevation meters
Position format (Latitude / longitude) ²	Hddd.ddddd = decimal degrees (6 decimal places)
Datum	wgs84
Map spheroid	wgs84
Heading	Numeric degrees North reference: true

Note: if you have any questions about how to configure your GPS, tell us the brand and model of GPS and we can help you

5. VEGETABLE COVER

It refers to the existence of herbaceous vegetation (size greater than 10 cm) in the plot at the time of sampling: (yes/no)

¹Francisco Javier Ariza López: fjariza@ujaen.es

²h = Hemisphere (North , South , East , or West)

d = Degree

6. PHENOLOGICAL STATUS OF THE OLIVE GROVE

Indicate the identifying letter of the phenological state of the olive tree

A.- Sprouting or spring bud.	B.- Development of leaf buds	C.- Flowering.
D.- Formation of the fruit.	E.- Development of the fruit.	F.- Veraison.
G.- Ripening.	H.- Picked fruit	I.- Pruning

7. WEATHER DATA OF THE DAY OF FIELD DATA CAPTURE

Although the data is imprecise, this information can be very useful to validate data collection. Mobile phones can provide us with information related to temperature. Precipitation and wind should be a subjective perception as there are no meters of these variables, however, the Beaufort classification in the case of wind will be taken as a reference, and the following Standard AEMET table for precipitation:

Temperature	Precipitation					Wind (Beaufort Scale)
	D.	m	F	MF	you	

Beaufort number	description	Wind speed	country conditions
0	calm	<2km/h	Smoke rises vertically
1	Light air	2–5 km/h	Direction shown by smoke drift but not by wind vanes
2	Light breeze	6–11 km/h	Wind felt on face; leaves rustle; wind vane moved by wind
3	Gentle breeze	12–19 km/h	Leaves and small twigs in constant motion; light flags extended
4	Moderate breeze	20–28 km/h	Raises dust and loose paper; small branches moved
5	Fresh breeze	29–38 km/h	Small trees in leaf begin to sway; crested wavelets form on inland waters
6	strong breeze	39–49 km/h	Large branches in motion; whistling heard in telegraph wires; umbrellas used with difficulty
7	High wind, moderate gale, near gale	50–61 km/h	Whole trees in motion; inconvenience felt when walking against the wind
8	Gale, fresh Gale	62–74 km/h	Twigs break off trees; generally impedes progress
9	Strong's /severe gale	75–88 km/h	Slight structural damage (chimney pots and slates removed)
10	Storm , whole gale	89–102 km/h	Seldom experienced inland; trees uprooted; considerable structural damage
eleven	violent storm	103–117 km/h	Very rarely experienced; accompanied by widespread damage
12	Hurricane - force ^[13]	≥118km/h	Devastation

Precipitation according to its intensity

Class	Average intensity in one hour (mm/h)
Weak	≤2
Moderate	>2 and ≤15
Powerful	>15 and ≤30
Very strong	>30 and ≤60
Torrential	>60

Source: AEMET

8. SAMPLING TYPE

to	linear	b	linear	c	linear
d	linear	and	linear	s1	Random on regular surface
s2	Stratified on regular surface	s3	On a grid	s4	zig Zag
s5	crossed	s6	traced	s7	grid center
s8	Regular points on circular surface	p1	Random points on plot	p2	Intersection point
p3	Square center point	you	under tree	either	other

9. DISTANCE TO THE TREE FROM THE SAMPLE POINT in cm

Measure the distance from the trunk to the sampling point in cm

10. SAMPLE DEPTH (CM, MM)

Measure the depth of the sample point and specify units

11. DATA OF THE PEOPLE WHO TAKE THE FIELD DATA

It is very important to identify the person who performs the data collection in the field, for this, it is necessary to attach the contact information of this person: name, telephone, mail

12. OBSERVATIONS:

Reserved field to record incidents related to georeferenced data that are not specific to the research area (weather incidents, GPS, etc.)